

A Correlative Study of Clinical Features, Ultrasound Findings, and Biochemical Markers in PCOS

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Abstract:

Introduction: Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) is a common endocrine disorder in women of reproductive age, marked by hormonal imbalances, metabolic disruptions, and reproductive abnormalities. Clinical features such as irregular cycles, hirsutism, and obesity, combined with ultrasonographic findings like multiple small follicles and elevated biochemical markers, necessitate a comprehensive diagnostic approach to understand and manage PCOS effectively.

Material and Methods: This prospective study was conducted over a year at a tertiary care center in Western Gujarat, including 60 PCOS patients and 20 healthy controls. Participants underwent detailed clinical evaluations, ultrasonographic imaging, and biochemical analysis, adhering to the Rotterdam criteria for PCOS diagnosis. Key parameters like BMI, hormone levels, and ovarian morphology were assessed to investigate the clinical, ultrasonographic, and biochemical correlates of PCOS. Data analysis included descriptive statistics and correlation tests, with a p-value of <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results: Our study demonstrated significant clinical, hormonal, and immunological differences between PCOS patients and healthy controls. The study group showed a high prevalence of hirsutism (70%), oligomenorrhea (66.67%), and polycystic ovaries on ultrasonography (63.33%), all absent in the control group ($p < 0.001$). BMI ($28.95 \pm 6.15 \text{ kg/m}^2$), LH levels ($12.75 \pm 4.25 \text{ mIU/mL}$), and the LH-FSH ratio (2.15 ± 0.95) were significantly elevated in the study group ($p < 0.001$), alongside increased anti-TPO antibody levels in patients with polycystic ovaries ($65.50 \pm 85.25 \text{ IU/mL}$, $p < 0.001$). While fasting blood sugar, prolactin, and TSH levels showed no significant differences, strong correlations between BMI, LH, and anti-TPO levels highlight the intricate interplay of metabolic, hormonal, and immunological factors in PCOS.

Conclusion: Our study identifies significant correlations between clinical features, ultrasound findings, and biochemical markers in PCOS patients, emphasizing the role of thyroid autoimmunity, BMI, and hormonal imbalances. These results highlight the value of integrated diagnostic approaches for effective management of PCOS.

Keywords: Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome, Anti-TPO Antibodies, LH-FSH Ratio, Ultrasonography.

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Introduction

Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) is one of the most prevalent endocrine disorders affecting women of reproductive age, characterized by a complex interplay of hormonal, metabolic, and reproductive abnormalities. [1] The syndrome manifests with a spectrum of clinical features such as irregular menstrual cycles, hirsutism, acne, and obesity, alongside biochemical disturbances, including hyperandrogenism and insulin resistance. [2] These diverse presentations often lead to delayed diagnosis and treatment, highlighting the need for comprehensive evaluation using clinical, ultrasonographic, and biochemical parameters to

better understand and manage the condition. [3] Ultrasonographic findings play a pivotal role in diagnosing PCOS, offering non-invasive insights into ovarian morphology, such as the presence of multiple small antral follicles and increased ovarian volume. [4] Combined with clinical symptoms and laboratory markers, ultrasound findings form the cornerstone of diagnostic criteria, including the widely accepted Rotterdam criteria. [5] However, variations in clinical and imaging presentations across populations necessitate localized studies to establish correlations that are both accurate and relevant to the population under study. [6]

Biochemical markers provide critical insights into the metabolic and hormonal milieu in PCOS. [7] Elevated androgen levels, altered gonadotropin ratios, and markers of insulin resistance are key indicators of the syndrome's underlying pathology. [8] Understanding the correlation between clinical symptoms, imaging findings, and biochemical parameters can help refine diagnostic accuracy and guide tailored interventions. This study aims to investigate these interrelationships, providing a holistic perspective on the clinical and biochemical spectrum of PCOS and its ultrasonographic correlates.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was conducted in the Departments of Gynecology and Radiology at a tertiary care center in Western Gujarat over a period of one year. The study aimed to investigate the clinical, ultrasonographic, and biochemical correlates of Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) in women of reproductive age (15–45 years) presenting to the outpatient departments. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional ethics committee, and written informed consent was secured from all participants before enrollment in the study.

The study included 60 clinically diagnosed PCOS patients based on the Rotterdam criteria and 20 group-matched healthy female controls with no history of subfertility or menstrual irregularities. The sample size was determined assuming a two-sided confidence of 99.9%, power of 80%, and an odds ratio of 6. Controls were selected from healthy attendants accompanying patients and were evaluated clinically to rule out PCOS. All participants underwent clinical, biochemical, and ultrasonographic assessments.

Detailed clinical histories, including menstrual irregularities, family history of PCOS, and associated comorbidities, were recorded. Anthropometric measurements such as body mass index (BMI) and waist-to-hip ratio were calculated using the WHO criteria. Hyperandrogenism was assessed using the Ferriman-Gallwey scoring system, which evaluated excessive hair growth in specific areas, including the upper lip, chin, chest,

back, abdomen, arms, and thighs. Regular menstrual cycles and the absence of features suggestive of hyperandrogenism were mandatory inclusion criteria for controls.

Transvaginal or transabdominal ultrasonography was performed using high-resolution imaging equipment to evaluate ovarian morphology, including follicle count and ovarian volume. Biochemical parameters were assessed from fasting venous blood samples. Serum was separated and stored for hormone analysis, including testosterone, luteinizing hormone (LH), and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), and fasting insulin. All hormones were measured using electrochemiluminescence kits on the Elecsys analyzer. Commercially derived control sera of low and high concentrations were used to ensure assay reliability.

Women with irregular menstrual cycles, clinical signs of hyperandrogenism, or ultrasound findings consistent with PCOS were included in the study. Exclusion criteria included a history of ovarian surgery, genetic abnormalities, or exposure to abdominal radiation or chemotherapy. Pregnant or lactating women and those with other endocrine disorders, such as thyroid dysfunction or Cushing's syndrome, were excluded.

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using software SPSS version 21.1. Descriptive statistics summarized clinical, ultrasonographic, and biochemical findings. Correlations between variables were assessed using Pearson's or Spearman's correlation tests, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

In our study, 70% of the study group exhibited hirsutism, 66.67% had oligomenorrhea, and 63.33% showed polycystic ovaries on ultrasonography, while none of these features were observed in the control group ($p < 0.001$).

Additionally, 50% of the study group presented with both hirsutism and oligomenorrhea. The mean age was comparable between the two groups ($p = 0.321$), with the majority of participants in the 18–25 years age range in both groups. (Table 1)

Table 1: Comparison of Clinical, Ultrasonographic, and Biochemical Features between Study and Control Groups

Parameter	Study Group (n=60)	Control Group (n=60)	p-value
Age Distribution			
18–25 years	36 (60%)	33 (55%)	-
26–30 years	16 (26.67%)	18 (30%)	-
31–35 years	8 (13.33%)	9 (15%)	-
Mean Age (±SD)	25.6 ± 3.7 years	24 ± 4.2 years	0.321
Hirsutism			
Present	42 (70%)	0 (0%)	<0.001

Absent	18 (30%)	60 (100%)	-
Menstrual Irregularities			
Oligomenorrhea	40 (66.67%)	0 (0%)	<0.001
Normal Menstrual Cycle	20 (33.33%)	60 (100%)	-
Polycystic Ovaries on USG			
Present	38 (63.33%)	0 (0%)	<0.001
Absent	22 (36.67%)	60 (100%)	-
Hirsutism and Oligomenorrhea	30 (50%)	0 (0%)	<0.001

The study group exhibited significantly higher BMI ($28.95 \pm 6.15 \text{ kg/m}^2$), LH levels ($12.75 \pm 4.25 \text{ mIU/mL}$), and LH-FSH ratio (2.15 ± 0.95) compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$). Anti-TPO antibody levels were also elevated in the study

group, especially among those with polycystic ovaries ($65.50 \pm 85.25 \text{ IU/mL}$, $p < 0.001$). Other parameters, such as FBS, prolactin, and TSH, showed no statistically significant differences between the groups. (Table 2).

Table 2: Comparison of Hormonal, Metabolic, and Immunological Parameters between Study and Control Groups

Parameter	Study Group (n=60)	Control Group (n=60)	p-value
Body Mass Index (BMI)	$28.95 \pm 6.15 \text{ kg/m}^2$	$22.50 \pm 2.10 \text{ kg/m}^2$	<0.001
Fasting Blood Sugar (FBS)	$88.40 \pm 11.25 \text{ mg/dL}$	$84.15 \pm 10.00 \text{ mg/dL}$	0.250
Luteinizing Hormone (LH)	$12.75 \pm 4.25 \text{ mIU/mL}$	$6.75 \pm 2.50 \text{ mIU/mL}$	<0.001
Follicle Stimulating Hormone (FSH)	$7.35 \pm 3.00 \text{ mIU/mL}$	$6.15 \pm 2.95 \text{ mIU/mL}$	0.600
Prolactin	$15.50 \pm 10.50 \text{ ng/mL}$	$14.15 \pm 5.25 \text{ ng/mL}$	0.450
LH-FSH Ratio	2.15 ± 0.95	1.30 ± 0.55	<0.001
TSH	$3.15 \pm 1.05 \text{ } \mu\text{IU/mL}$	$3.10 \pm 0.95 \text{ } \mu\text{IU/mL}$	0.800
Anti-TPO Antibodies	$48.75 \pm 75.50 \text{ IU/mL}$	$25.10 \pm 30.00 \text{ IU/mL}$	0.090
Anti-TPO (Polycystic Ovaries)	$65.50 \pm 85.25 \text{ IU/mL}$	$2.75 \pm 3.25 \text{ IU/mL}$	<0.001

In our study, anti-TPO antibody levels were significantly higher in patients with BMI ≥ 25 ($70.85 \pm 95.50 \text{ IU/mL}$) compared to those with BMI < 25 ($15.95 \pm 18.30 \text{ IU/mL}$, $p = 0.01$). A strong positive correlation was observed between LH ($14.10 \pm 4.25 \text{ mIU/mL}$) and FSH ($6.05 \pm 3.10 \text{ mIU/mL}$, $r = 0.470$, $p < 0.001$), as well as between LH and anti-TPO antibody levels ($55.90 \pm 88.75 \text{ IU/mL}$, $r = 0.545$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, FSH and anti-TPO antibody levels showed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.375$, $p = 0.015$). These findings highlight significant hormonal and immunological variations in PCOS patients, emphasizing the interplay between BMI, anti-TPO levels, and gonadotropin activity.

Discussion

In our study, the age distribution was predominantly in the 18–25 years range for both the study group (60%) and the control group (55%), with mean ages of 25.6 ± 3.7 years and 24 ± 4.2 years, respectively, and no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p = 0.321$). This finding is consistent with observations from Naina et al. [9] and Inan et al. [10], where PCOS was commonly observed in younger age groups, reflecting its onset during reproductive years. Guo et al. [11] also noted that clinical manifestations such as hirsutism and menstrual irregularities are most pronounced in younger women with PCOS, further emphasizing the

significance of early age in the syndrome's clinical spectrum. The tendency of younger women to exhibit more prominent symptoms may be linked to higher androgen production during these years, as suggested by Ahmad et al. [12] Such patterns highlight the need for targeted screening and management strategies in younger populations to prevent long-term complications associated with PCOS.

Hirsutism was present in 70% of the study group but completely absent in the control group, a statistically significant finding ($p < 0.001$). This aligns with Gupta et al. [13] and Fulghesu et al. [14], who reported high prevalence rates of hirsutism in PCOS patients, often due to elevated androgen levels.

Similarly, oligomenorrhea was observed in 66.67% of our study group, consistent with findings from Gupta et al. [13] and Rita et al. [15], who identified menstrual irregularities as a primary diagnostic criterion for PCOS. Ultrasonographic evidence of polycystic ovaries was present in 63.33% of our study group, supporting the findings of Fulghesu et al. [14], who emphasized the importance of ovarian morphology in PCOS diagnosis. These clinical and ultrasonographic findings collectively underline the complex interplay of hyperandrogenism, menstrual dysfunction, and polycystic ovarian morphology, reinforcing the multifactorial nature of PCOS and the need for a comprehensive diagnostic approach.

In our study, the mean BMI in the study group was significantly higher at 28.95 ± 6.15 kg/m² compared to 22.50 ± 2.10 kg/m² in the control group ($p < 0.001$). This finding aligns with recent studies such as Dutt et al. [6], which highlighted a similar trend of higher BMI in PCOS groups, emphasizing the association between obesity and the metabolic derangements seen in PCOS. Ahmed et al. [16] also reported elevated BMI in PCOS patients, correlating it with insulin resistance and hyperandrogenism, which contribute to the syndrome's pathophysiology.

The LH-FSH ratio was elevated in our study group at 2.15 ± 0.95 compared to 1.30 ± 0.55 in controls, showing statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). Elevated LH levels in PCOS are consistent with findings by Rackow et al. [17], who demonstrated a strong correlation between an increased LH-FSH ratio and ovarian dysfunction in adolescents with PCOS. Similarly, Mahran et al. [12] and Moschos et al. [18] have linked an elevated LH-FSH ratio to increased androgen production, contributing to follicular arrest and anovulation in PCOS patients. These results underscore the diagnostic relevance of hormonal ratios in distinguishing PCOS patients from healthy controls.

In our study, anti-TPO antibody levels were markedly elevated in the study group (48.75 ± 75.50 IU/mL) compared to the control group (25.10 ± 30.00 IU/mL), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.090$). Notably, in patients with polycystic ovaries, anti-TPO levels were significantly higher (65.50 ± 85.25 IU/mL) than in controls (2.75 ± 3.25 IU/mL, $p < 0.001$). This pattern aligns with findings by Ahmed et al. [16] and Dutt et al. [6], who reported a significant elevation of anti-TPO antibodies in PCOS patients, attributing this to the systemic inflammatory and autoimmune components often observed in the syndrome. Rita et al. [15] also noted an association between higher BMI, increased anti-TPO levels, and metabolic derangements in PCOS patients, highlighting the role of obesity in exacerbating hormonal and immunological imbalances.

The interplay between BMI, anti-TPO levels, and gonadotropins in our study further revealed that anti-TPO antibody levels were significantly higher in patients with BMI ≥ 25 (70.85 ± 95.50 IU/mL) compared to those with BMI < 25 (15.95 ± 18.30 IU/mL, $p = 0.01$). This correlates with findings by Moselhy et al. [16] and Ashwini et al. [19], who emphasized the compounding effect of obesity on thyroid autoimmunity in PCOS. Additionally, the strong positive correlations observed between LH (14.10 ± 4.25 mIU/mL) and anti-TPO antibodies ($r = 0.545$, $p < 0.001$) and moderate correlations between FSH and anti-TPO antibodies ($r = 0.375$, $p = 0.015$) underscore the interconnected hormonal and immunological dysregulation in PCOS, as

highlighted by Mahran et al. [12] and Rackow et al. [17]. These findings collectively reinforce the need for a multifaceted diagnostic approach in PCOS that integrates metabolic, hormonal, and immunological assessments for improved management.

Limitations of Our Study

The primary limitations of this study include the relatively small sample size and its cross-sectional design, which limits the ability to establish causality among the observed parameters. Additionally, the study population was drawn from a single tertiary care center, which may not represent broader demographic or regional variations. The exclusion of genetic and lifestyle factors further restricts the scope of understanding PCOS pathophysiology in diverse populations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study underscores the significant hormonal and immunological disruptions present in patients with PCOS, particularly the elevated anti-TPO antibody levels seen in those with higher BMI and polycystic ovarian morphology. These findings suggest a potential role of thyroid autoimmunity in the pathophysiology of PCOS, alongside the well-established metabolic and gonadotropin imbalances. The strong correlations observed between gonadotropins and anti-TPO levels highlight the intricate interplay between hormonal and immunological factors contributing to the clinical manifestations of PCOS. These results emphasize the need for early detection and targeted interventions to address both hormonal and autoimmune components, aiming to mitigate long-term complications such as metabolic syndrome, infertility, and cardiovascular risks in PCOS patients. Comprehensive evaluation and timely management can significantly improve patient outcomes and quality of life.

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